

THE PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDYING THE CREATIVE EXAMPLES OF ANVAR OBIDJAN IN PRIMARY CLASS READING LESSONS

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Abstract. *The article focuses on the essence, goals and tasks of primary school reading classes. The educational importance of using Anvar Obidjon's creative examples and their role in educating young people as a well-rounded person during the school period will be highlighted in the reading classes.*

Keywords: *the purpose of the lesson, mother nature, seasons, folklore, love of work, friendship, patriotism.*

First President Islam Karimov said, "We have achieved independence, and our noble intention is to build a great and free society in the future. Our strategy is based on the upbringing of a healthy generation and is aimed at its development", he emphasized many times in his many lectures, speeches and conversations with the young generation. Yes, children's literature, which is an integral part of adult literature, i.e., reading lessons, is very important in raising the young generation to become perfect people, as our late president dreamed. By studying the works of children's writers in various genres, primary school reading classes prepare the next generation to be physically strong, spiritually pure, mentally healthy, full of faith, knowledgeable, moral, and courageous. and is distinguished by the great and complex task of raising a brave, patriotic generation.

The student is faced with the ability to read the text correctly, quickly, understand it, and master its content for the first time in the reading classes. Through the reading classes, students will be able to acquire knowledge, skills and knowledge that are expected to be mastered by the requirements of the State Education Standard. It is in reading education that a person's desire to understand himself, and secondly, the world, is stimulated.

For this purpose, the "Reading Book" textbooks include various topics such as mother nature, the world around us, the history and present image of our country, the lives of adults and children, hard work, independence and national-spiritual values, friendship and peace among peoples. artistic, moral-educational, scientific-popular works designed to provide comprehensive understanding of the topics are included.

If reading lessons are organized in the period of literacy training in the form of introducing students to syllables, words and sentences and reading them, telling stories based on pictures, after mastering the reading technique, reading becomes a certain it is conducted on the basis of selected artistic, scientific and popular texts.

The specific topics included in the "Reading Book" textbooks of the primary grade are determined by bringing students into the magical world of fiction, focusing on the correct formation of their worldviews based on the ideology of national independence. Accordingly, the leader of the reading classes feature is focused on educating students in the spirit of high moral values on the basis of national ideology while ensuring students' literacy.

The subjects chosen for the reading classes are intended to provide students with knowledge and education on everyday life, strengthening of independence and human relations. Among them, the themes of independence, homeland, spirituality and nature stand out. Their goal is to create self-awareness, independence, homeland and nature.

Topics such as patriotism, the world around us, hard work are among the comprehensive topics in textbooks, and we observe that children's writer Anvar Obidjon also meets examples of these topics in his creative work. The poem "Berkinmachok" included in the "Yashnaydi Olam" section, the poem "Good intention" from the "Ilm-Aql Chirogi" section, "My motherland is my golden cradle" in the 2nd grade "Reading book" "My Uzbekistan" section, "Work brings happiness" section, "I will become a man" section, "Silver winter-example of a swan" section, etc. will be analyzed.

For example, we will analyze the poem "Berkinmachok" included in the section "The world flourishes" in the 1st grade "Reading book":

Three comrades together	If I want to hide, I
Me, Aziza and Koshok	Every tulip spells slowly,
In the bosom of a wide tulip field	He says: "Come on boy,
We played hide and seek	Bekin in our space".

Through this poem, Anvar Obidjon tried to arouse thoughts such as attitude towards nature, spring season has arrived, nature has woken up, tulips have opened and love nature, based on simple concepts, using the game of hide and seek. we can see.

Let's look at the poem "My Uzbekistan" in the section "My motherland is my golden cradle" in the 2nd grade "Reading book" by Anvar Obidjon.

My dear country, I see you
Your maple trees are like ours.
A stone is also in the soil of flowers,
Your mercy is in the hot spring.
You have many open gardens,
There are many mines for the treasury.
Your village, city is living,
Give your all to goodness...

In the above poem, the poet has described the strengthening of independence, love of the motherland, its beauty, natural resources and natural landscapes through beautiful lines. The purpose of this is to realize one's identity, to awaken feelings related to independence, homeland and nature.

I'll think again
All good work.
I will not be lazy,
Don't you worry.
I'm going to be... a man, Dad!
- well – done, my son!

The poem "I will become a man" in the section "Work brings happiness" is based on a conversation between a father and a child. It shows the process of telling his father about the boy's dream of getting various professions. The fact that the boy first wanted to be a chauffeur, and then became interested in space, a football player, and became a doctor was somewhat humorous. At

the end of the conversation, it was concluded that the child should not be lazy and be a person. This will increase children's love for professions.

The poet tries to show the greatness and richness of our native language in the poem "Teacher's lessons" in the section "Generous autumn" in the 3rd grade reading book, comparing each word to a sprout. calls for use. In the poem, the poet instills in the readers that the value of a person lies in his country, nation and language.

Anvar Obidjon's works, written with pleasure, inspiration and love, fulfill all tasks conscientiously: these poems are both a cheerful friend and a serious educator. His poems have the power to captivate any reader through strange, sweet humor, hidden pity, laughter and tears, regular persistence, mysterious expressions, and unexpected allusions.

As can be seen from the above, in the creative examples of the poet in the reading classes, social issues are imposed on the events that occur in real life. On the basis of the created humor, along with various vices in people's relationships, major social issues that belong to the whole nation are revealed through unexpected details and circumstances. The created social images and the ideas put forward are worthy of recognition as the basis of social life. This indicates the social nature of Anvar Obidjon's comics.

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